

Assessment of Instructional Materials and Teaching Methodologies on Implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the Instructional materials and Teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two specific objectives. Two research questions and hypotheses, respectively. The Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The total population of the study was 737 stake holders comprising 102 head teachers, 588 Nomadic teachers and 47 quality assurance officers. The sample size was 248 stake holders (37 head teachers, 195 Nomadic teachers and 16 quality assurance officers). Data were collected using a structured questionnaire title: "Evaluation of the Implementation Nomadic Education Programme in Zamfara State of Nigeria (EINEP)" was adopted by the researcher, the questionnaire was validated by the experts in the Department of Educational Foundations and Curriculum, Faculty of Education Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and after the pilot study, the data collected was statistically analysed for reliability co-efficient using Cronbach Alpha at a 0.05 significance level, and the reliability coefficient of 0.87 was obtained. Data collected were analysed using bar chart to answer the research questions while Kruskal-Wallis H test was used to test hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that Instructional materials were not adequately provided for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State, Nigeria, among others. The study concluded that implementation of Nomadic education programme in Zamfara state was generally low. It was recommended that Governments at all levels should ensure that Nomadic schools are provided with adequate and relevant instructional materials.

Keywords: Instructional materials, Methods of teaching & Nomadic Education Programme.

Introduction

Education is the springboard for social and economic change and plays a major role in the socio-economic development of a nation. Education occupies an important place in most plans for economic and social development. It is important in human development as a supplier of the trained manpower as well as a requisite for the accomplishment of other development goals (Adebiye, 2014). The roles played by the educational sector stimulate the economic growth and development which explains why countries expend so much on education in order to enhance the level of literacy of their citizenry. This is why inequality of access to education and educational marginalization has serious effects on national development.

The constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999) as amended stated that the "Government shall direct its policy towards ensuring that there are equal and adequate educational opportunities". In this regard, the children of nomadic pastoralist, whose parents are contributing daily to the growth and development of the country's economy, should not be left behind un-educated. The nomadic children should have access to formal education and efforts should be made to ensure that functional and productive education is provided to them.

The National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014) demands that every Nigerian child should have full access to quality education at basic education level. However, the attainment of this objective is not easy as pointed Bolaji, Yusuf, Jekayinfa and Mofoluwawo (2010) to nomads who wander from place to place with no fixed home, makes it difficult to have their children enrolled in schools.

The National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) (2012) is of the view that the movement of nomads is necessitated by their economic activities. These activities engaged by nomads is used to describe their ethnic, social and as professional group of people that move from one place to another in search for means of survival (Kratli, 2011).

According to Muhammad and Abbo (2010) posit that the Nigerian nomadic pastoralists are made up of the Fulani (5.3m), Shuwa (1.01m), Koyam (32,000), Badai (20,000), Dark Buzzu (15,000) and the Buduma (10,000). The Fulani are found in 31 out of the 36 States of Nigeria, while others reside mainly on the Borno plains and shores of Lake Chad. The migrant fishing groups account for about 2.8 million, comprising numerous tribes. They are found in the Atlantic coastline, the riverside areas and river basins of the country. These groups of people amongst others do not have access to functional education in the country over time. In the quest to remove the chronic illiteracy among this mobile population of Nigeria, the federal government of Nigeria introduced Nomadic Education Program (NEP) in 1986. The NEP was designed to provide the nomads with the relevant and fundamental basic education that would improve their survival skills. This was expected to provide them with the knowledge and the skills that would enable them to raise their productivity and income; as well as empower them to participate effectively in the socio-economic and political affairs of the country.

The main aim of nomadic education is to take education to the nomads. In this regard, a mobile system of education was designed to be used where the nomads are far from conventional nomadic primary schools or where the nomads are in continuous movement. Most of the Nomadic schools adopted the conventional fixed school system. The implication is that since the government cannot establish schools in every community, some of the nomads found themselves in communities with no nomadic primary school nearby.

After establishing nomadic primary schools in most states of the Federation by the NCNE, there has been a shortage of manpower as most of the teachers in continued to seek transfer to conventional schools. Educational resources have also been in short supply in most nomadic primary schools. Lack of adequate funding has been largely blamed for the inadequate educational resources. To make things worse, there seems to be a lukewarm attitude by supervisors of some of these schools in difficult terrains as supervision of schools in these areas leaves little to be admired (Akwe, 2018).

In a progress report on a nomadic education programme in Nigeria submits that classroom accommodation still remains the most acute problem of the nomadic education programme. While classroom furniture is lacking in the majority of the schools including the ones that have built classrooms, the report also points out that instructional materials such as chalk, chalkboards, textbooks, visual and audio aids are in short supply in most of the nomadic primary schools in the states. Thus, it is difficult to fully implement the curriculum for nomadic education in the centres that experience these challenges. Another disturbing factor capable of obstructing the implementation of the nomadic education curriculum is the unavailability of manpower (trained teachers) (Kana, 2012).

To implement is to put into action or operation a plan or a system, this according to Iwovi in Kolawole (2013) observe that implementation is the translation of theory into practice or a proposal into action. Curriculum implementation is a stage of putting into practice all that has been documented as curriculum in the classroom through the combined effort of the teachers, learners, school administrator, parent as well as interaction with the physical facilities, instructional materials, psychological and social environment of the school (Onyeachu in Kolawole, 2013).

Nomadic Education is the first six years of Basic Education provided to the children of disadvantaged nomadic populations in the country (FRN, 2014). This is formal education designed for the transmission of knowledge from one generation of nomads to another. In Nigeria, nomadic education was specifically established for nomadic children who did not have the opportunity to attend conventional schools because of their parents' occupation. It began during the colonial period but actual firm government involvement started in 1986 when it was officially introduced by the then military administration of General Ibrahim Babangida (Akpan, 2015).

Nomadic education as defined by Tahir (1997), is the informal education provided by the nomadic people within their cultural contexts as well as the formal and non-formal education provided by the nomads, national governments and international agencies aimed at promoting the culture of the nomadic peoples and equipping them with relevant knowledge and skills to empower them to develop themselves and their communities. This will also enable them to contribute to national development. Therefore, in considering the education of nomads for national development in Africa, the discussion will be centred on their traditional education, the attempts made by international agencies and national governments to educate them, and the structure and scope of the education provided for them in some African countries and how such educational provisions promote their culture and development in their communities and nations.

According to NCNE cited in Abbo (2011), the initiative into the NEP includes the activities and projects aimed at producing adequate and well-trained teachers for the NEP and to improve the quality of instruction. Prior to these initiatives, there were not enough teachers in nomadic schools to the extent that teacher: pupil ratio was as high as 1:80 in certain cases.

The available teachers were mostly unqualified, poorly trained and inexperienced in dealing with the nomads. They had the background and training for teaching in the conventional school system suitable for the sedentary mainstream population since the teachers knew nothing about the nomadic groups and could not put their special needs and circumstances into proper focus. They used inappropriate and ineffective teaching methods and materials resulting in poor classroom interaction and low learning achievement of pupils.

Curriculum can be defined as the sum total of all systematically planned learning experiences prepared by the organization responsible for teaching a specific group for the achievements of an individual's specific goals and those of the society in general. Buckhad (1998) and Lar (2010) observe that there is the need to design a functional curriculum for the nomads, which must be of symbiotic relationship with the target society the ideology of the nomadic culture, belief system and environment. According to them, it is the relevance of the curriculum that will change the attitudes of the nomads and motivate their children to respond to education positively.

The NCNE has considered the development and institutionalization of relevant curriculum a priority in its effort to provide education for the nomads. The commission in developing the curriculum paid special attention to the fact that the nomadic pastoralists have peculiar needs, lifestyles, work rates and environment. Therefore, whatever should form the content of education for their children should consider these peculiarities. The commission adopted the existing primary school curriculum into the unique socio-cultural and economic pattern of life of the nomads.

The Nomadic Education Centre (NEC) located at the Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, which is statutorily assigned the function of the curriculum development, carried out the development and adaptation of curriculum for the nomadic pastoralist according to Uyanga and Siddique (2000) the exercise involved adaptation from the existing national core curriculum for primary schools and subject areas thus: English, Mathematics, Primary Science, Social Studies, Hand Craft, Health Education, Islamic Religious Knowledge and Fulfulde.

Subject specialists and experts with sufficient knowledge of the culture, educational needs and problems of the nomadic pastoralists were utilized for the adaptation, process. In doing this, an attempt was made to make each objective child-centred and the contents were scrutinized for relevance with the objectives and the needs and condition of the nomads; irrelevant contents were removed or modified and replaced with more ones that are relevant. The main aim of the nomadic education curriculum is to make schooling more appealing to nomads as well as to transform pastoralist society more effectively.

Bruner (1973) says that the teachers work as a communicator, model and identification figure can be supported by wise use of a variety of devices that expand the experience, clarify it and give it personal significance. Agun (2000) refers to them as learning materials, the proper use of which helps learners to learn faster and better. Similarly, Obanya (1989) view them as didactic materials-things which are supposed to make learning and teaching possible while according to Johnson (1989) instructional materials are the collections and selection of resources (mechanical, otherwise) from available resources which are applied and integrated into a systematic process of teaching and learning to make learning effective. Ikerionwu (2000) refers to them as objects or devices, which help the teacher to make a lesson for the learner. Instructional materials, therefore, are concrete or physical objects which provide sound, visual or both to the sense organs during teaching (Agina-Obu, 2005). According to Abdullahi (2010), instructional materials are materials or tools locally made or imported that could make tremendous enhancement of lesson impact if intelligently used. In most cases, many learners have the difficulty in understanding certain concepts because of their level of cognitive operation, it is against this background that Jean Piaget postulated human beings to be classified along with sensory-motor, pre-operational, concrete and abstract cognitive levels. On the importance of the usage of instructional materials in nomadic primary schools, Aliyu and Mohammed in Ogbondah (2008) stated that "the success of any educational programme depends on proper planning and the availability and utilization of resources. Therefore, a successful lesson has to do with effective use of instructional materials". Similarly, where the modern instructional materials are not available or cannot work effectively in rural areas for instance television and computers, Nomadic school teachers are to be creative in improvising instructional materials.

With regards to the provision of instructional/infrastructure the National Commission of Nomadic Education observed that there is an inadequate supply of instructional materials such as textbooks, exercise books, writing materials and copies of subjects-curricular. Similarly, facilities such as classrooms and furniture are grossly inadequate (Situation Report on Nomadic Education 2002).

The teaching/learning style of the nomadic people must be understood by teachers and used to teach the nomads. Curricula/content Concepts must be illustrated using the objects and examples drawn from their culture and environment to make their learning easy and meaningful. This has guided the orientation and training of teachers and supervisors of nomadic schools organized by the National Commission for Nomadic Education. According to NCNE cited in Abbo (2011), the

initiative into the NEP includes the activities and projects aimed at producing adequate and well-trained teachers for the NEP and to improve the quality of instruction. Prior to these initiatives, there were not enough teachers in nomadic schools to the extent that teacher: pupil ratio was as high as 1:80 in certain cases. The available teachers were mostly unqualified, poorly trained and inexperienced in dealing with the nomads. They had the background and training for teaching in the conventional school system suitable for the sedentary mainstream population since the teachers knew nothing about the nomadic groups and could not put their special needs and circumstances into proper focus. They used inappropriate and ineffective teaching methods and materials resulting in poor classroom interaction and low learning achievement of pupils.

The pedagogical teacher development initiatives for improving Nomadic Education Programme were geared towards achieving the following objectives: Produce and retain the critical mass of teachers needed to attain the goals of the NEP, train new teachers with nomadic backgrounds, re-train serving teachers to understand and appreciate the peculiar needs and circumstances of the nomads, acquaint teachers, supervisors and coordinators with the rationale, policy, objectives and strategies of the NEP, enhance knowledge, skills and competences of nomadic teachers through the use of innovative teaching methods and improve lesson delivery; improve classroom interaction and learning achievement.

There is Agency for Nomadic education in Zamfara State; the function of the Agency for Nomadic Education in the state is to impart knowledge and functional survival skills for improving the efficiency and productivity of the Nomads towards the realizations of specific national goals. The agency has also to do with the recruitment, appointment, promotion, posting, transfer, and discipline of the nomadic teaching and non-teaching staff of the schools under the agency. There are 49 Nomadic primary schools across the state with 169 academic staff. Enrolment of pupils stood at 4,723 – 3,209 male and 1,514 female in 2015. There are also 103 classes out of which 54 need renovation and require additional 66 classes. There are three tarpaulin classes supplied by the National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) in 2014, seven motorcycles for monitoring were supplied by the NCNE in 2013. Some textbooks and curricular models were supplied by the commission in 2015 Four Hundred and Fifty (450) core subject textbooks were also supplied in 2014 by the commission (ZSG, 2017).

Theories and Models are useful in programme evaluation because they provide a set of steps that could be followed in carrying out a proposed evaluation, they are very important in the understanding of concepts used in education, they are carefully selected in line with the topic. Therefore, the researcher reviews the theory of Human Capital Theory. This theory was propounded by a renowned economist called Adam Smith in 1776. Oni opines that human capital theory has gained currency since the time of Adam Smith, but its popularity was however, emphasized by Theodore Schultz in his 1990 presidential address to the American Economic Association (AED). Human capital theory is relevant to the study based on comprehensiveness, establishing procedures for maximizing the impact of study results on institutional decision making and investment in the education of the nomads/shepherds children. In addition, the theory of human capital which became popular after the Second World War has generated certain responses from many interest groups. No doubt the consequence of these responses has been the increasing investment in education as a means of accelerating the rate of economic growth of the society and this adopted the theory because of its relevance to the development of nomadic and shepherd schools educational programme in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Also, Stufflebeam's CIPP model of evaluation was reviewed by the researchers. Context, Input, Process, Product and Constraints (CIPPC) model which is a modified form of Stufflebeams (1971) Context, Input, Process and Product (CIPP) model was used in this study. This model according to Achebe (2004) is used to evaluate a programme about the context in which it operates the input of the programme process through which students go and the product of the programme as well as the problems militating against the implementation of the programme. This theory is relevant to the current study because it gave insight on the process/steps of evaluation. Context evaluation was being employed to diagnose the programme problems about the determination of the aims and objectives of the programme in the State.

Different research works have been conducted on Nomadic Education, most of which reviewed by the researchers have been found conducted in Nigeria. Among are those conducted and reviewed by the researcher are; Saidu, Abudu, Odebode and Oyeyemi (2017), studied on historical analysis of NEP in Kwara State, Nigeria: 1988-2011, Abubakar (2015) carried out research to determine the impact of the Nomadic Education Programme on the Nomads Employment Opportunity and Cattle production Output in the North-West zone of Nigeria, also Yaguya (2014) assessed the impact of the nomadic education curriculum on the educational development of nomads in Nigeria among others. This present study assessed the Instructional materials and Teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The study was guided by the following specific objectives, which are to:

1. determine the efficacy of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State;
2. Examine the efficacy of teaching methodologies on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State.

Research Questions

The followings are research questions:

1. What is the impact of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?
2. What is the impact of teaching methodologies on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?

Hypotheses

The following Null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level:

1. There is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State;
2. There is no significant difference between Choice of teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive survey research design following the recommendation of Dada (2016) who stated that descriptive survey research is a detailed study, which strives to explain or determine and report the way things are. It is the type of research that specifies the true nature of a given problem or event. The descriptive survey research further involves assessing situations through the administration of instruments that are specifically prepared for such a purpose. The choice of descriptive survey design for this research was based on the fact that the entire population cannot be covered, and so a sampling procedure would be done. The population of this study comprised of all 102 Nomadic primary schools in all 14 Local Government Areas (LGAs) of three (3) senatorial districts in Zamfara State. The population comprised of one hundred and two (102) Head teachers, five hundred and eighty-eight (588) Teachers and forty-seven (47) Quality Assurance officials, totaling seven hundred and thirty-seven (737) (ZMSANE, 2020).

A sample size of 248 participated in the study. This is based on the recommendation by the Research Advisors (2006), which recommends that for a population of 700-799 a sample size of 248 is sufficient for generalization at 95% confidential level and 5% margin of error.

A multi-stage sampling procedure to select the respondents. In the first stage, a proportionate sampling procedure was used to distribute the sample among the elements of the population (Head teachers, Teachers and Quality Assurance Officials) where Sulaiman (2015), explained that proportionate sampling is used when the elements of population vary considerably in size because it assures that those in larger size have the same probability of getting into the sample as those in the smaller size, and vice versa.

At the second stage, the LGAs and Nomadic primary schools were purposively selected based on recommendation by Dada (2016) who said in purposive sampling, researcher uses own judgment in selection of members of the population. It is used to obtain a representative sample by using a sound judgment, which will result in the collection of reliable data, saving time and money.

At the third stage, convenient sampling technique was used by the researcher to select the Head teachers, Teachers and Quality Assurance Officers which Agbe (2003) opined is also known as grab sampling or opportunity sampling is the type of non-probability sampling that involves the sample being drawn from that part of the population that is close to hand. The research instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire that was adopted by the researchers. The questionnaire was made in two parts, A and B. Part A contained the respondents' general information while Part B consist of 20 item or statements about the objectives of the study using four (4) points modified Likert scale of 4- SA (Strongly Agree), 3- A (Agree), 2- D (Disagree) and 1- SD (Strongly Disagree). The data collected was analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. Bar chart were used to present responses of the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using nonparametric statistics of Kruskal-Wallis H test which deals with the three independent sample groups in the study. This test

is used to determine if there are statistically significance differences among three or more groups of independent variable on continuous or ordinal dependent variable by researcher (Kruskal and Wallis, 1952).

Results

Research Question 1: What is the impact of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?

Figure 1: Responses of the respondents on the impact of Instructional Materials in Nomadic Primary Schools in Zamfara State

Source: Field work, (2021)

Figure 1 above describes the respondents' views to the questionnaire from item 1-10

Figure 1 shows the result of the opinion of impact of instructional materials on implementation of NEP in Zamfara State. The finding presented indicated that most of the respondents are not in agreement with the majority of the items and this revealed that instructional materials were not adequately provided in Nomadic Schools for the implementation of NEP in Zamfara State.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of teaching methodologies on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State?

Figure 2: Responses of the respondents on the Instructional Methods used by Nomadic Primary Schools Teachers in Zamfara State

Source: Field work, (2021)

Figure 2 above describes the respondents' views to the questionnaire from item 11-20.

The result presented above in Figure 2 shows the responses of the respondents on the instructional methods used by Nomadic school teachers for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State. The result presented indicated that most of respondents did not agree with the items. This shows that the majority of Nomadic school teachers are using inappropriate teaching methods for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State;

Table 1: Kruskal-Wallis (H) test on the responses of the respondents on the Provision of Instructional Materials in Nomadic Primary Schools in Zamfara State

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	$H(X^2)$	Df	α	Sig.	Decision
Teachers	205	124.40	25.48	2	0.05	0.21	Retained
Headteachers	27	112.30					
Quality Assurance	16	146.23					

Source: Field work, (2021)

Table 1 presents the Kruskal-Wallis (H) test to determine the provision of instructional materials for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State. The result of the Kruskal-Wallis (H) test shows that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State; was retained. This is because the Mean Rank of 124.40, 112.30 and 146.23 for the three groups of respondents, $H(X^2)$ of 25.48 and p-value 0.21 > $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance was obtained. Therefore, the null hypothesis was retained.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant difference between choice of teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State.

Table 2: Kruskal-Wallis (H) test on the responses of the respondents on the Instructional Methods used by Nomadic Primary Schools Teachers in Zamfara State

Respondents	N	Mean Rank	$H(X^2)$	Df	α	Sig.	Decision
Teachers	205	105.14	117.80	2	0.05	0.00	Rejected
Headteachers	27	227.83					
Quality Assurance	16	198.18					

Source: Field work, (2021)

Table 2 shows the result of a test of hypothesis four, which says there is no significant difference among the responses of the respondents in the instructional methods used by Nomadic Education teachers for implementing the NEP

curriculum in Nomadic primary schools of Zamfara. The result of the Kruskal-Wallis (H) test as shown above shows that a significant difference exists among the opinion of respondents in the instructional methods used by Nomadic teachers for the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State. It shows that the Mean rank of 105.14, 227.83 and 198.18 for the three (3) groups of respondents, $H(X^2)$ of 117.80 and p-value $0.00 < \alpha=0.05$ level of significance was obtained. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of Findings

This section discussed the findings of the study, alongside the findings of other researchers, also the discussion is based on the variables contained in the study which were guided by the research questions and research hypotheses tested. Firstly, finding number one reveals the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between availability of instructional materials on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State was retained. The study also concluded that instructional materials were not adequately provided for the implementation of the Nomadic NEP in Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding is in agreement with Ada (2014) whose finding in the study on the impact of communal crises on nomadic education in Plateau State revealed that there is a poor state of educational resources for nomadic education in Plateau State. This finding is also in line with Duze (2011) who found that educational resources were lacking in implementing nomadic education curriculum in Nigeria.

The second finding revealed that the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between choice of teaching methodology on implementation of Nomadic Education Program in Zamfara State was rejected. Also, the study concludes that conventional methods are mostly used by Nomadic teachers in the implementation of the NEP in Zamfara State, Nigeria. This finding is in line with Ogbondah (2008) in a study on Appraisal of instructional materials used to educate the Fishermen Children in Rivers State that most of the teachers are not qualified and cannot effectively utilize the available instructional materials for the effective implementation of migrant fishermen's children education programme.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that both the objectives and goals of the Nomadic education programme have not been achieved and therefore, the implementation of Nomadic Education Programme in Zamfara state was generally low.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

1. Governments at all levels should ensure that Nomadic schools are provided with adequate and relevant instructional materials;
2. Head Teachers and quality assurance officers should encourage Nomadic teachers to apply the appropriate teaching method when and where necessary

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References

- Abbo, B. M. (2011). Implementing Nigerias Nomadic Education Programme (NEP). *Journal of Commonwealth Education Partnerships*, 2(4).
- Abdullahi, A. (2010). *Science Teaching in Nigeria*, Atoto Press.
- Abubakar, B. (2015). Analysis of the Impact of Nomadic Education Programme on Cattle Production Output and Employment Opportunities in North Western Zone of Nigeria. Unpublished Masters Dissertation, Submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.
- Achebe, V.N. (2004). Evaluation of the basic literacy programme of the national mass
- Ada, O. (2014). The impact of communal crisis on nomadic Education Curriculum in Plateau State. Jos Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis University of Jos Plateau State.

- Adebiyi, M. A. (2004). Public Expenditure and human capital in Nigeria: An Autoregressive Model. *International Journal of Economics*, 1(3), 86-77.
- Agbe, N. N (2003). *Fundamentals of Research Reporting in Education: A Practical Approach*. (2nded.) : Sifers.
- Agina-Obu, T. N. (2005). The Relevance of Instructional Materials in Teaching and Learning in Robert-Okah, I & Uzoeshi, K.C. (Eds). *Theory and Practice of Teaching*: Harey Publication.
- Agun, I. (2000). Learning Materials Towards Education in the year 2000. *Journal of Educational Media Technology*, 1(4), 498–521.
- Akpan, L. O. (2015). An investigation into the history of nomadic education policies in Nigeria, 1986-2009. A Thesis submitted in fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy Faculty of Education, University of KwaZulu-Natal
- Akwe. I. P. (2018). Evaluation of the Implementation of Nomadic Education Curriculum and its Impact on Socio-Economic and Educational Development of Nomads in Nasarawa and Plateau States, Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis. Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Curriculum and Instruction.
- Bolaji, A. Yusuf, H. T., Jekayinfa, A. A. & Mofoluwawo, E. O. (2010). *Education for all in Nigeria: Reaching out to the Nomadic population*. *African Journal of historical Science in Education*. 6, (2), 20 – 30.
- Burkhadt, B. (1998). The role of indigenous knowledge system (IKS) in popularizing science Education: An Evaluation of the IKS Inclusive Science Curriculum for Nomadic Primary Schools in Northern Nigeria. Unpublished research proposal submitted to institute of education, University of Ibadan Nigeria.
- Dada, A. A. (2016). *Conducting Research in Education*, Nigeria, Concepts Design and Prints.
- Diso, M.A. & Haruna, A.S. (2020). History Students' Preference for Lecturers' Gender and Achievement in a History Course in Colleges of Education in Kano State. *Kano Journal of Educational Psychology* 2(2), 278-277.
- Duze, C.O. (2011). Administrative constraints affecting curriculum development and implementation in Nigeria: towards education for sustainable development. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa* 13 (8), 1-8.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (1999). *Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999*. University Press.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria, (2014). *National Policy on Education*. NERDC Publishers.
- Ikerionwu, J. C. (2000). *Importance of Aids and Resources in Classroom Teaching, in Perspective of Classroom Teaching*. In Oyeneyin, A.M. (ed), Martmonic investment Ltd.
- Johnson, H. I. (1989). Relevant Instructional Materials in Family Life Education for Nigerian Secondary schools. A paper delivered at the workshop on Population/Family Life Education Material Development, organized by NERDC/CEDPA/Johnson- Hopalang University 23rd - 29th April at Dubar Hotel, Lagos.
- Kana K. (2012). Report on the Teachers and Pupils Distribution of Nomadic primary schools in Nasarawa State. National Commission for Nomadic Education, Nasarawa State.
- Kolawole, C. O., (2013). *Transforming Basic and Secondary Education in Osun State Through Effective Implementation*. Foremost Educational Services Limited.
- Kratli, S. (2011). *Education provision to nomadic pastoralist*. A literature Review: Brighton IDS Working Paper 26. Nomadic centre, University of Jos.
- Kruskal, W. H. & Wallis, W. A. (1958). Use of Rank in One-Criterion Variance Analysis, *Journal of the American Statistical Association* 47(260), pp 583-621.
- Lar, M. (2010). *Nomadic Education in Nigeria; Way forward in the new Millennium*: workshop proceedings by Nomadic centre, University of Jos, Plateau State, Nigeria.
- literacy in the south east zone of Nigeria. Unpublished PhD Thesis Submitted to the School of Postgraduate Studies, University of Nigeria, Nsukka.
- National Commission for Nomadic Education (NCNE) (2012). Printed and bound in Kaduna, Ezeoma Printer Limited.
- Obanya, P. A. I. (1989). Potentialities of Educational Materials in Africa, in *Inter-learning of Educational Innovation*. UNESCO/BREDA, 55-64.
- Ogbondah, L. (2008). An Appraisal of Instructional Materials Used to Educate Migrant Fishermen's Children in Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 1(1) 13-25. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/An-Appraisal-of-Instructional-Materials-Used-to-in-Ogbondah/4a4f75de1fb899e652bfb7d63e0a43b3f70126de>
- Research Advisors (2006). Determining the Sample Size. <https://www.research-advisors.com/tools/SampleSize.htm>

- Saidu, A., Abudu, Z. A., Odebode, A. A. & Oyeyemi, J. J. (2017). Historical Analysis of Nomadic Education Programme in Kwara State, Nigeria: 1988-2011. *Kampala International University Journal of Social Sciences* 3(2): 333–341.
- Stufflebeam, D. L. (1971). *Evaluation for decision-making*. Illinois Peacock Inc.
- Sulaiman, H. (2015). Assessment of the Implementation of Universal Basic Education
- Tahir G. (1997). Functions, Problems and Prospects of Nomadic Education in Nigeria. A submission presented to the sub-committee on education of vision 2010.
- Uyanga, A. & Siddique, S. (2000). Development of Relevant Curriculum for Disadvantaged Groups. The case of the nomadic pastoralists and migrant fishing communities in Nigeria. in Abba & Kanu (Eds). *Education of the Disadvantage Groups in Nigeria*. AfaBAnich Nigeria limited.
- Yaguya, N. A. (2014). Impact of nomadic education curriculum on the educational development of nomads. *Global Journal of Arts Humanities and Social Sciences* 3(4):68-73.
- Zamfara State Agency For Nomadic Education (ZMSANE) (2019). Annual School Census Report (2019/2020).
- Zamfara State Government (ZSG) (2017). Education Sector Medium Term Sector Strategy 2015 – 2017: Ministry of Education, Gusau.